

NDAC/LO/027

1983 Sept 2

Fifth NDAC Report from Lund Observatory (Addendum, July - August, 1983)

1. WP6200: PRS Solution, Algorithm Development (Söderhjelm)

A report on the small-scale experiments has been distributed (024). Work is now concentrating on data organisation problems.

2. WP8100: Double Stars, Definition (Lindegren)

Work on this task has just begun and should be completed by mid-October.

3. Dynamical Smoothing, Photometry (Lindegren)

It is suggested to introduce polynomials in the Set Solution to represent the attitude around $\underline{z}$ for intervals (superframes) of the order of 100 s. This and possible further extensions towards DS have been studied, mainly from the algorithmic point of view, in (025).

Analytical expressions have been derived for the photometric errors of the IDT signal parameters. An important result is that the second harmonic has practically zero weight for photometry (026). The structure of the normal equations for the photometric calibration has been studied (1983 Aug 12).

4. References

- NDAC/LO/024 Small-Scale Experiments in Step 2 With Elimination of Set Orientations (9 pp)
- NDAC/LO/025 Dynamical Smoothing: Inclusion of Attitude Continuity Conditions in the Set Solution (22 pp)
- NDAC/LO/026 Covariance of the Photometric IDT Signal Parameters (29 pp)
- NDAC/LO/027 Fifth NDAC Report from Lund Observatory (Addendum, July - August, 1983) (1 p)
- 1983 Aug 12 Formation and Solution of Normal Equations for Photometry (3 pp)